

COVID-19: Malaysian Lifestyle and Preventive Behaviours during Movement Control Order

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INTRODUCTION

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RESPONDENT PROFILE

RESULTS

LIFESTYLE BEHAVIOURS

SMOKING

Smoking Status	Percentage
Smokers	10.3%
non-smokers	89.7%
Smokers with intention to quit smoking	
With intention	46.7%
no intention	53.3%

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Practice a sedentary lifestyle (prolonged sitting >30 minutes daily)	69.0%
Practice a sedentary lifestyle (screen time >30 minutes daily)	85.5%
Most frequent activity at home	
• internet surfing	18.8%
• cooking/house chores	18.2%
• sit/recline continuously	16.9%
• watching television	16.9%
• exercise	14.4%
• others	8.8%
• gardening	6.0%

EATING BEHAVIOUR

Complete daily intake of main meals (breakfast, lunch and dinner)	
Complete	72.4%
Did not complete	28.6%
Breakdown of daily main meals intake	
Breakfast	84.3%
Lunch	93.5%
Dinner	89.0%
Complete daily intake of food groups (carbohydrates, protein, fruits, vegetables, and milk & dairy products)	
Complete	45.1%
Did not complete	54.9%
Breakdown of daily food group intake	
Protein	98.3%
Carbohydrates	98.1%
Vegetables	90.5%
Fruits	74.7%
Milk & dairy products	58.2%

Food eating behaviour

Home cooked food	94.4%
Drink at least 8 glasses of plain water a day	73.8%
Eat more often than usual	46.5%
Drink sugar-sweetened beverages more often than usual	27.7%
Eat fast / instant food more often than usual	18.1%

PREVENTIVE BEHAVIOURS

RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS COVID-19 PREVENTIVE MEASURES

Main preventive measures	
Clean & disinfect house	99.0%
Wash hands regularly	98.9%
Practice social distancing	98.8%
Wear face mask	98.3%
Stay at home	98.1%
What to do when sick	
Seek medical advice	98.8%
Avoid meet others	99.1%
Disclosing travel history to healthcare provider for purpose of contact tracing	99.1%
Notify the nearest clinic / hospital if any family / household Member has COVID-19 symptoms	99.4%
READINESS FOR BEHAVIOUR CHANGE AFTER MCO	
Wash hands with water & soap regularly	99.0%
Wear a face mask if have fever & cough	97.7%
Practice Social Distancing	96.0%
Avoid crowded places & limit social gatherings	40.5%

EFFECTS OF MOVEMENT CONTROL ORDER (MCO)

ENFORCEMENT OF MCO

It can prevent spread of COVID-19	98.4%
Worried MCO will be extended	55.8%
Worried when government announced MCO	53.6%
Bored of repetitive daily activity at home	42.1%
MCO disrupts daily routine	33.7%
Felt stressed being confined at home	30.0%
FAMILY RELATIONSHIP	
Family / household relationship become more closer	94.8%
Worried about the safety of family living apart	86.7%
Often fight with couple / family during throughout MCO	7.1%
PANIC BUYING	
Bought food supply more than usual	50.9%
Worried food supply on the market are insufficient	39.2%
WORK / STUDY FROM HOME	
Worried of MCO effect on work/education	73.7%
More productive working/learning from home	44.1%
FINANCIAL	
Worried source of income affected because of MCO	57.9%
Worried if government financial support is insufficient	57.3%

DISCUSSION / CONCLUSION

Significant behaviour changes were identified during MCO. Continuous efforts in promoting healthy lifestyle and encouraging positive behaviour changes are needed in reducing COVID-19 transmission and embracing the "New Normal".

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